

Management Approaches for Ectopic Pregnancies in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Ectopic pregnancy is a chief causal factor to maternal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing nations. This condition occurs when a fertilized egg implants outside the uterine cavity, requiring swift diagnosis and intervention to prevent life-threatening complications. The incidence, risk factors, clinical manifestations, management approaches, and outcomes of ectopic pregnancies vary significantly depending on demographic and healthcare factors.

Aim: The aim of this study is to examine the clinical presentation, associated risk factors, treatment modalities, and outcomes in patients diagnosed with ectopic pregnancies.

Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted over two years, from August 2022 to July 2024, at MKCG Medical College and Hospital, involving 180 patients diagnosed with ectopic pregnancies. Comprehensive patient data, including demographics, risk factors, clinical presentations, and past surgical or obstetric histories, were collected. Management was categorized as either medical or surgical, depending on the patient's condition. Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS Version 21.0. Statistical significance was evaluated using the Student's t-test and Chi-square test.

Results: The incidence of ectopic pregnancy was found to be 1.17%, with the highest occurrence in women aged 26-30 years. Hemoglobin levels between 7-9.9 gm% were observed in 41.6% of the patients. Ampullary tubal pregnancy was the most common site of implantation (85%), and 81.1% of cases involved ruptured ectopic pregnancies. Unilateral salpingectomy was the most frequently performed surgical procedure (88.3%). Blood transfusions were necessary in 53.8% of cases, and the mortality rate was 1.6%.

Conclusion: Ectopic pregnancy continues to pose a serious health challenge with notable morbidity and mortality. Early diagnosis and timely management are essential to improving outcomes. Surgical intervention remains the primary treatment option, especially in cases of ruptured ectopic pregnancies.

Recommendations: To reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with ectopic pregnancies, it is recommended to strengthen antenatal care, promote early ultrasound screening, and raise awareness among healthcare providers and patients regarding the risk factors for ectopic pregnancies.

Keywords: Ectopic Pregnancy, Clinical Presentation, Risk Factors, Management Strategies, Obstetric Outcomes.

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Introduction

Ectopic pregnancy is a serious and potentially life-threatening obstetric condition in which a fertilized egg implants outside the uterus, most commonly within the fallopian tube. This abnormal implantation disrupts the natural course of pregnancy, making it non-viable and potentially leading to severe complications if not addressed promptly. These complications include tubal rupture, internal hemorrhage, and, in severe cases,

maternal death. Timely diagnosis and intervention are crucial to prevent these outcomes and reduce the burden of morbidity and mortality associated with ectopic pregnancies [1,2]

Globally, ectopic pregnancies account for approximately 1-2% of all pregnancies, though this figure may vary based on geographical region, healthcare infrastructure, and population-specific risk factors. In resource-limited settings, such as

many developing countries, the challenge is compounded by delays in diagnosis and limited access to appropriate healthcare services. Often, patients present at an advanced stage, when life-threatening complications have already developed, necessitating urgent medical or surgical intervention. Therefore, understanding the local demographic and clinical trends of ectopic pregnancy is key to improving management outcomes in these contexts [3,4]

The management of ectopic pregnancy is broadly categorized into medical and surgical approaches, depending on the clinical scenario. Medical management, often with methotrexate, is a non-invasive option for stable patients with early-diagnosed ectopic pregnancies. It works by stopping cell division and allowing the body to naturally resolve the ectopic tissue. However, in more advanced cases, particularly those involving tubal rupture or significant bleeding, surgical intervention becomes necessary. Salpingectomy, which involves the removal of the affected fallopian tube, is the most frequently performed procedure in these cases [5]

In tertiary care hospitals, where complex and high-risk pregnancies are frequently managed, healthcare professionals have access to advanced diagnostic tools, such as transvaginal ultrasounds and high-level laboratory tests, allowing for earlier detection and more effective treatment. These hospitals are also equipped with surgical teams and intensive care units, making them the ideal setting for managing complications associated with ectopic pregnancies. Timely surgical intervention in ruptured cases is often life-saving, underscoring the importance of specialized care in these facilities.

This study seeks to explore the treatment modalities for ectopic pregnancies within a tertiary care hospital setting. By examining the clinical characteristics, management strategies, and outcomes of these patients, the research aims to highlight the effectiveness of different approaches and identify ways to optimize care delivery, thereby improving patient outcomes and reducing complications associated with this potentially fatal condition.

1. Methodology

Study Design and Setting: This study was a prospective, hospital-based observational study conducted over a period of two years, from June 2022 to June 2024, in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at MKCG Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur. The study aimed to evaluate the treatment modalities for ectopic pregnancies in this tertiary care setting.

Participants: The study included 180 women of reproductive age who were diagnosed with ectopic

pregnancy and admitted to the hospital during the study period. Participants presented to the outpatient department (OPD) or labor room with clinical symptoms indicative of ectopic pregnancy, which were subsequently confirmed by diagnostic tests.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: The inclusion criteria encompassed all cases of ectopic pregnancy admitted during the two-year study period. Women with confirmed intrauterine pregnancies or spontaneous abortions were excluded from the study to maintain the focus on ectopic pregnancies.

Bias Minimization: To reduce selection bias, all eligible patients diagnosed with ectopic pregnancy during the study duration were consecutively enrolled. Information bias was minimized by utilizing a standardized data collection proforma and ensuring that all medical personnel involved in the study were adequately trained in data collection procedures.

Variables: The primary variables assessed included demographic information (age, residence, education level, socioeconomic status), clinical symptoms (missed periods, vaginal bleeding, abdominal pain), associated risk factors (smoking, pelvic inflammatory disease, previous ectopic pregnancies, use of intrauterine devices, sterilization, in vitro fertilization, previous cesarean section), and treatment methods (medical management or surgical intervention).

Data Collection: Data were gathered through structured interviews and clinical evaluations of each participant. A comprehensive history was obtained, documenting demographic characteristics, clinical symptoms, and potential risk factors. Participants underwent general and obstetrical examinations, and diagnostic tests such as urine pregnancy tests (UPT), complete blood counts (CBC), ICTC, HbsAg, and ultrasonography (USG) were conducted to confirm the diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy.

Procedure: The management of patients depended on their clinical presentation and condition. Treatment options included medical management with methotrexate or surgical interventions, which consisted of procedures such as salpingectomy, salpingo-oophorectomy, cornual repair, or hysterectomy. The requirement for blood transfusions was also recorded. Intraoperative findings, including the site of the ectopic pregnancy and whether it was ruptured or unruptured, were documented. Patients were followed until discharge or death, with all relevant clinical data entered into a standardized proforma.

Statistical Analysis:

The collected data were initially processed using Microsoft Excel 2019 and then imported into SPSS Version 21.0 (IBM, IL, Chicago) for statistical

analysis. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to assess the relationships between variables and treatment outcomes.

Results

A prospective observational study was carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at MKCG Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur, from June 2022 to June 2024. The study aimed to assess the clinical presentation, associated risk factors, treatment strategies, and outcomes of ectopic pregnancies. During this period, 15,350 pregnant women were admitted to the hospital,

among which 180 cases were diagnosed as ectopic pregnancies, resulting in an incidence rate of 1.17%. Furthermore, around 70 cases of unruptured and chronic ectopic pregnancies were lost to follow-up as they opted for treatment in private hospitals under the BSKY scheme.

Incidence of Ectopic Pregnancy: Out of the 15,350 total pregnancies admitted, 180 were diagnosed as ectopic pregnancies, yielding an incidence rate of 1.17%.

Table 1: Incidence of Ectopic Pregnancy

Category	Count	Percentage (%)
Ectopic Pregnancy	180	1.17%
Total Pregnancies	15,350	100%

Age Distribution: The distribution of ectopic pregnancy cases showed that the highest number occurred in women aged 26-30 years (31.2%), followed by the 31-35 years age group (27.3%).

Table 2: Age Distribution of Subjects (n=180)

Age Group (Years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<20	11	6.1%
21-25	48	26.6%
26-30	56	31.2%
31-35	49	27.3%
36-40	11	6.1%

Educational Background: Most patients had secondary education (46.2%), with 41.1% having only primary education. A smaller portion had achieved graduate (10.5%) or higher levels of education (2.2%).

Table 3: Educational Distribution of Subjects (n=180)

Education Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Primary	74	41.1%
Secondary	83	46.2%
Graduate	19	10.5%
Higher Studies	4	2.2%

Parity: The majority of patients were multigravida (78.9%), with 37.3% being in their second pregnancy (G2), 30.5% in their third (G3), and 11.1% having four or more pregnancies (G4 or higher).

Table 4: Parity Distribution of Subjects (n=180)

Parity	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Primigravida (G1)	38	21.1%
Multigravida (G2)	67	37.3%
G3	55	30.5%
G4 and more	20	11.1%

Risk Factors: The most common risk factors identified were previous abortions (23.3%), a history of pelvic inflammatory disease (18.3%), and dilation and curettage (12.2%). Other significant factors included sterilization (10%), abortifacient intake (11.1%), and intrauterine device use (7.7%).

Table 5: Risk Factors among Subjects (n=180)

Risk Factor	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Previous Abortions	42	23.3%
Smoking	5	2.7%
In Vitro Fertilization (IVF)	0	0%
Intrauterine Device (IUD)	14	7.7%
Sterilization	18	10%
Pelvic Inflammatory Disease (PID)	33	18.3%
Dilation and Curettage (D&C)	22	12.2%
Previous Ectopic	2	1.1%
Abortifacient Intake	20	11.1%

Clinical Presentation and Hemoglobin Levels: The majority of patients presented with abdominal pain (91.1%) and amenorrhea (78.3%). Hemoglobin levels showed that 41.6% of the patients had levels between 7-9.9 gm%, while 5.5% had critically low levels below 4 gm%.

Table 6: Hemoglobin Levels among Subjects (n=180)

Hemoglobin Range (gm%)	Count	Percentage (%)
<4	10	5.5%
4-6.9	33	18.3%
7-9.9	75	41.6%
10-10.9	34	18.8%
>11	28	15.5%

Site of Ectopic Pregnancy and Intraoperative Findings: The ampulla of the fallopian tube was the most common site for ectopic pregnancies, accounting for 85% of cases. A significant portion of these pregnancies (81.1%) were ruptured upon diagnosis. Surgical intervention was required in 95% of cases, with unilateral salpingectomy being the most common procedure performed (88.3%).

Table 7: Site of Ectopic Pregnancy Implantation (n=180)

Site of Implantation	Count	Percentage (%)
Tubal — Ampulla	153	85%
Tubal - Isthmus	15	8.3%
Tubal - Infundibulum	3	1.6%
Cornual	2	1.1%
Caesarean Scar	2	1.1%
Ovarian	4	2.2%
Heterotopic	1	0.5%

Management and Surgical Findings: Most patients underwent surgical management, with 95% requiring laparotomy and only 4.4% managed laparoscopically. Hemoperitoneum, or blood in the peritoneal cavity, was present in varying degrees, with 55% of cases having 500-1000 ml of blood, and 9.4% having more than 1500 ml. Blood transfusion was necessary in 53.8% of cases, and the mortality rate was 1.6%.

Table 8: Management and Intraoperative Findings of Ectopic Pregnancy (n=180)

Procedure or Treatment	Count	Percentage (%)
Unilateral Salpingoophorectomy	16	8.8%
Unilateral Salpingectomy	159	88.3%
Cornual Resection and Repair	2	1.1%
Hysterectomy	2	1.1%
Medical Management	1	0.5%
Hemoperitoneum <500ml	24	13.3%
Hemoperitoneum 500-1000ml	99	55%
Hemoperitoneum 1000-1500ml	40	22.3%
Hemoperitoneum >1500ml	17	9.4%
Laparoscopy	8	4.4%
Laparotomy	171	95%
Need for Blood Transfusion	97	53.8%
Mortality	3	1.6%

Discussion

The study revealed an incidence rate of 1.17% for ectopic pregnancy, with the majority of cases occurring in women aged 26-30 years. Most of the patients had a secondary education level and were multigravida. Abdominal pain was the predominant symptom, and many patients presented with anemia, highlighting the severity of their condition. Most ectopic pregnancies were located in the ampulla, and a large proportion were ruptured at the time of diagnosis, requiring urgent surgical intervention. Blood transfusions were necessary for more than half of the patients, and the mortality rate stood at 1.6%, emphasizing the importance of prompt diagnosis and treatment.

Ectopic Pregnancy and Maternal Health Impact

Ectopic pregnancy continues to be a significant contributor to maternal morbidity and mortality, particularly during the first trimester. Globally, ectopic pregnancies account for 10-15% of first-trimester maternal deaths, underscoring the importance of prompt detection and treatment. The incidence of ectopic pregnancy in this study was 1.17%, which is consistent with other studies. For instance, Ritu Gupta et al. [6] reported an incidence of 2.461 per 1000 deliveries in Rajasthan, and Deepali Kharat et al. [7] observed a 0.76% incidence in a Mumbai tertiary care hospital. Variations in incidence rates between regions may reflect differences in healthcare access, diagnostic capabilities, and data recording standards.

Age Distribution and Risk Factors

The majority of ectopic pregnancy cases occurred in women aged 26-30 years (31.2%), aligning with findings from Gandhari Basu et al. (33.9%) [8] and Deepali Kharat et al. (62.9%) [7]. This peak incidence can be attributed to various reproductive health factors such as prior dilatation and curettage (D&C), previous abortions, and intrauterine device (IUD) use, all of which are recognized risk factors for ectopic pregnancies. As women in this age group are typically in their reproductive years, cumulative reproductive health factors play a significant role.

Educational and Socio-Economic Factors

Educational background and socio-economic status have a notable impact on health outcomes in ectopic pregnancy cases. In this study, most patients had only primary (41.1%) or secondary (46.2%) education and belonged to lower socio-economic groups. Similar findings were reported by Gandhari Basu et al. [8] and Deepali Kharat et al., [7] where 82.2% and 88.1% of patients, respectively, were from lower socio-economic classes. Limited awareness and inadequate access to healthcare may contribute to the increased risk of ectopic pregnancy and delayed diagnosis in these populations.

Parity and Multiparity as Risk Factors

Multiparity was observed in 78.9% of the patients in this study, mirroring findings from Deepali Kharat et al. (82.5%) [7] and Tahmina et al. (72.2%) [10]. The high prevalence of multiparity among ectopic pregnancy patients can be attributed to accumulated risk factors over multiple pregnancies, such as pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), previous abortions, and contraceptive device use. These risk factors can lead to tubal damage, increasing the likelihood of ectopic implantation in subsequent pregnancies.

Clinical Presentation and Hemoglobin Levels

Abdominal pain was the most common symptom, affecting 91.1% of patients, followed by amenorrhea (78.3%) and abnormal vaginal bleeding (63.3%). These findings are consistent with studies by Mridula Srivastava et al., [10] where 81% of patients experienced abdominal pain, and Hassan et al., [11] where 70.97% had abdominal pain. The classic triad of pain, amenorrhea, and vaginal bleeding was present in 50% of patients, comparable to 76.5% in Deepali Kharat et al. [7] and 40.3% in Tahmina et al. [10]. The prevalence of these symptoms highlights the importance of early symptom recognition for timely intervention.

Risk Factors for Ectopic Pregnancy

The most common risk factors identified were previous abortions (23.3%), D&C (12.2%), sterilization (10%), and IUD use (7.7%). These risk factors are in line with findings from other studies, such as Mridula Srivastava et al. [10] (23.4% for previous abortions) and Tahmina et al. [10] (36.1% for abortion history). Additionally, pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) was observed in 18.3% of cases, a rate similar to those reported by Tahmina et al. (15.3%) [10] and Deepali Kharat et al. (13.9%) [7]. These risk factors contribute to tubal dysfunction, increasing the likelihood of ectopic pregnancy.

Site of Ectopic Implantation

Ampullary implantation was the most common site, observed in 85% of cases. This finding is consistent with studies by Archana et al., who reported ampullary implantation in 42.5% of cases, and Deepali Kharat et al.,⁽⁷⁾ who found rates of 56% and 44.9%. Right-sided ectopic pregnancies were more common, seen in 53.8% of cases, which is comparable to the 62% right-sided implantation reported by Mridula Srivastava et al. [10]

Management Strategies and Surgical Outcomes

Surgical intervention was the primary treatment modality, with 88.3% of patients undergoing unilateral salpingectomy, in line with other studies where salpingectomy was the most common procedure. Delayed presentation, ruptured ectopic

pregnancies, and hemodynamic instability were key factors necessitating surgery. A large proportion of patients (81.1%) presented with ruptured ectopic pregnancies, highlighting the critical importance of early detection and prompt surgical intervention to manage the condition effectively.

Mortality and Implications for Healthcare Access

The study reported three deaths (1.6%), all resulting from ruptured ectopic pregnancies presenting in shock. This mortality rate underscores the life-threatening nature of delayed diagnosis and intervention in ectopic pregnancy. It emphasizes the need for improving early detection, referral systems, and access to timely healthcare to reduce the risk of fatal outcomes in such cases.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the continued significance of ectopic pregnancy as a critical maternal health issue. There is a pressing need for increased awareness, better healthcare access, and robust referral systems to enable early diagnosis and intervention, reducing both morbidity and mortality associated with ectopic pregnancies.

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